

AN ANALYSIS OF PRICE DISCRIMINATION IN THE AIRLINE INDUSTRY

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Abstract

This paper analyzes price discrimination in the airline industry, focusing on its sources, types, and impact on social welfare. The study reviews existing literature and finds that airlines commonly use price discrimination to charge different prices to passengers based on their willingness to pay and demand elasticity. The findings show that third-degree price discrimination is the most widely used form in the airline industry, while evidence of first- and second-degree discrimination is limited. The paper also concludes that price discrimination can increase social welfare and is most effective in imperfectly competitive markets.

Keywords: Price discrimination, airline industry, social welfare, demand elasticity, third-degree price discrimination, monopoly, imperfect competition.

Introduction

Today, it is no secret that price discrimination can be found in most industries, especially in companies with high fixed costs. It implies that companies charge various prices from various customers, and they cannot explain it by variation of costs. The passenger airline industry is the prime example for it as they use different prices; although the cost of one flight does not depend on the number of passengers, it mostly depends on the cost of fuel and airport service prices. The current paper will discuss the influence, nature, source, and price discrimination types in the airline industry.

Literature review

Influence of price discrimination on social welfare

It is observed that price discrimination has many effects on social welfare. The quantity of products sold indicates a price change because some of customers' purchases more due to lower prices while others buy less amount because of higher prices in the industry. In this case, the distribution of goods and services occurs in an inappropriate manner. Therefore, consumers who are buying less product because of higher prices decide to end purchasing the good or service (Deneckere and McAfee, 1996). According to the research done by John Lazarev (2013), a data sample of US Airline

Market leaders shows that more than $\frac{3}{4}$ passengers buy airline tickets for leisure pursuits, and 90% of these individuals begin searching for a ticket 1.5 months before departure. By comparison, another group of people who plan their flights for business purposes try to purchase a week before departure. These travelers are ready to pay more (up to six times) for the flight, and business people contribute to price inelasticity of demand. (Lazarev, 2013)

Effects of price discrimination on social welfare can be discussed by three cases which all of them would be positive. One of the cases as follows: In a secondary market of airline tickets, the average price of tickets purchased by individuals who want flight for leisure purposes would increase by more than \$40 (from \$77 to \$118), and the quantity of tickets would indicate decline by 10%. However, business people's tickets experience different cases (price decline from \$382 to \$118; quantity growth by 49%). Taking all data into account, the average airline route indicated a 12% growth in social welfare.

The Nature and Source of Airline Price Discrimination.

In their work, Severin Borenstein and Nancy L. Rose (1994), in order to show what things cause price discrimination, they started by analyzing it in imperfectly competitive markets. In general, price discrimination in monopoly markets is mostly limited to demand elasticity in the consumer population and cannot be sustained under perfect competition. This means that as the market becomes less concentrated, price discrimination will decrease. However, according to findings provided by Holmes (1989) and Borenstein (1989), price discrimination will likely increase when the market changes from monopoly to imperfect competition. In the airline context, that would be a single carrier charging “full price” to business travelers (whose elasticity of demand is low) and “discount price” to ordinary travelers with high elasticity of demand. In case of entry by a new carrier, the incumbent will have lower prices for both groups. While under imperfect competition, a firm may price a specific customer depending on his or her cross-elasticity of demand among other companies (airlines or flight hours).

In the research done by Pattison (1973), determinants of elasticities analysis have been made. The author notes that the airline industry market is not a homogenous type and is divided into various forms. He observed that seven main areas of market segregation exist that have been the primary price discrimination source. These are:

- 1) duration of stay,

- 2) traveling days,
- 3) age limits,
- 4) day vs. night departures,
- 5) complementary inputs,
- 6) first-class fare vs. economy class,
- 7) Geopolitical consideration.

Also, in his research, Pattison finds out that the propensity of airlines to be in monopolistic competition rather than in pure monopoly has led to attracting new customers who might otherwise not have flown. This is especially true for American senior and youth citizens who are not able to use charter airlines.

Types of price discriminations in airline industry

The research conducted by Joanna Stavins (1996) studies the price discrimination and changing of prices for tickets in the Airline market of the United States; she collected data for flights on 12 different routes on the same day. According to the observed data, it was detected that the price of tickets on Holidays and Weekends differs from the prices on normal working days, which can be count as third-degree price discrimination. To analyze logically the airline industry of US dividing consumers into two groups, buyers on Weekends and buyers on working days, which is the element of third-degree discrimination. From another side, the number of tickets is also divided into two groups, the number of tickets that are selling for Weekends and working days, which is the element of the second degree. (Stavins, 1996)

Another research conducted by Galyna O. Chornous and Lulia A. Larmolenko (2020) represents 920 flight price observations' data tells the contrast. After analyzing the cases of geographical location, duration of the stay, and day of the week to purchase the tickets, it has been detected that Ukraine's air industry does not exist first and second-degree price discriminations. According to the geographical location, the Ukraine airline industry does not use the different prices according to the countries' status; for example, the prices to European countries are not higher than the countries of CIS, the prices are setting up according to the distance and fuel consumption. From the case of the day of the week to purchase tickets logically was detected that there is not second-degree price discrimination as the prices of tickets on Weekends did not differ from working days, but there is exist some discounts for children till age 12, which is the element of third-degree price discrimination. (Chornous and Larmolenko,

2020). According to all researches mentioned above, it was concluded that third-degree price discrimination exists almost in all airline companies, but there is not enough evidence of usage of first and second-degree price discriminations, but they exist in some companies.

Welfare effects of third degree price discrimination in monopoly

A casual observation conducted by Steen and Sorgard (2002) included different types of price discrimination in the airline market. Initially, there are many versions to choose tickets among, such as expensive ones, flexible ones, and cheap tickets with restrictions, such as Saturday night stay-over or advance-purchase. According to the research done by Steen and Sorgard, another typical example of price discrimination is writing a contract with airline companies. (Steen and Sorgard, 2002).

The theory of price discrimination is commonly related to a situation with a monopoly firm. In a monopoly, the company does better by practicing the third degree of price discrimination, different prices are charged to different customers, but each pays a constant price for each unit purchased. This type of discrimination gives a hand to airline companies selling tickets to some group of consumers more expensive with inelastic demand and lower prices to another group with elastic demand and spur their demand. This may reduce welfare for society, however. Higher price for the group with inelastic price demand brings deadweight loss, while the lower price for another group with inelastic price demand decreases in dead weight loss.

Another one big question comes out if third-degree price discrimination comprises that new group of members is served well. The monopoly firm may consider that it is more

profitable to serve only the price inelastic group of consumers. Therefore, competition has more advantages in any part of every sphere of business. (Varian, 1989).

Conclusion

From all exposed data above, it can be concluded that the price discrimination in monopoly markets is mostly limited to demand elasticity in the consumer population and cannot be sustained under perfect competition. From the Pattison's (1973) point of view, there are seven primary sources of price discrimination, such as duration of stay, traveling days, age limits, day vs. night departures, complementary inputs, first class fare vs. economy class and geopolitical consideration. According to the Joanna Stavins (1996) and Galyna O. Chornous and Lulia A. Larmolenko (2020) researches, it can be concluded that the third-degree price discrimination is the most common type of discrimination among airline industry. In addition, it can be mentioned that there was not enough prove for commonly usage of first and second degree price discriminations till now. Another interesting point is that price discrimination can increase the social welfare. In general, all researches helped us to understand the importance of price discrimination in economy and proof that the monopoly market is the most preferable structure for price discrimination.

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